

Social sciences & Humanities for Achieving a
Responsible, Equitable and Desirable GREEN DEAL

SHARED GREEN DEAL – GUIDELINES AND FAQ FOR CALL FOR LOCAL EXPERIMENT PARTNERS

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1. What are the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments about?

1.1 What is the objective of the call?

SHARED GREEN DEAL is offering local and regional authorities (including municipalities, cities, towns, villages and their local municipally owned companies and agencies) and not-for-profit organisations (e.g. NGOs, civil society organisations, associations, etc.) the opportunity to run social experiments focused on the following six priority Green Deal topics (Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, Preserving Biodiversity), all of which contribute to the climate action and zero pollution ambitions of the EU Green Deal.

Utilising diverse participatory approaches to involve local stakeholders and citizens, the experiments will address the behavioural, social and cultural dimensions of the Green Deal. The social experiments aim to facilitate and learn from change processes at both individual and collective levels whilst collecting research data in the process.

SHARED GREEN DEAL will provide financial support of up to EUR 22,000 to each municipality or not-for-profit organisation that commits to run a local social experiment.

24 European locations will be selected to run the social experiments (4 locations/stream).

The experiments have specific objectives according to each of the six streams covered:

- **Clean Energy:** Imagine your community's future, powered by energy that keeps our air clean and communities healthy! In this experiment stream, you will get to work with different members of your community to design this future and help make it happen. Using a community visioning approach, we will work with you to support various communities (e.g. citizens from a range of ages, local and national policy representatives, business employees) with imagining their own energy futures and build their capacity to plan for those futures. We will produce practical recommendations to advance the energy transition through collaborative approaches and by focusing on clean energy as well as energy demand.
- **Circular Economy:** This experiment stream aims to support circular business innovation. We are looking for applicants who will establish Local Accelerator Hubs (LAHs) that will gather and share knowledge about good practices in sustainable and circular business models to support innovation in 10+ local businesses and nudge the introduction of circular economy concepts; identify local needs and challenges; and co-create solutions. The experiment will organise a series of workshops and a local circular award event to reward the best solutions of the local businesses registered in the LAH using business innovation to optimise waste prevention and elimination and increase the use of circular strategies for new products and services. We encourage applicants to bring their own circular economy focus, based on local priorities that matter to them.
- **Efficient Renovations:** The buildings we live and work in require urgent upgrade and renovation to respond to the pressing demands of climate change. This experiment stream is looking for local partners who will help bring members of the community together to form a social network for understanding why renovation matters and what can be done for buildings' and inhabitants' needs. The experiment aspires to provide interactive learning opportunities, through events such as eco-tours so that participants can gain inspiration, practical knowledge and guidance in the process.
- **Sustainable Mobility:** This experiment stream will explore and shape the current mobility habits around travel to school. You will have an opportunity to co-create knowledge and interventions,

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through local mobility labs within schools, together with young people and other relevant stakeholders to support the transition towards sustainable school mobility in your city. It will enable young people's voices to feed into the development of policy recommendations at the local level using age-appropriate, playful approaches.

- **Sustainable Food:** This experiment stream will accelerate transformations towards more just and sustainable food systems. We will empower local initiatives to foster transformative change. Together we will explore the local context, identify key food system players and organise a series of meetings during which we develop an action agenda. SHARED GREEN DEAL partners will support you in learning about and applying transition governance methods.
- **Preserving Biodiversity:** In this experiment stream we will explore the different values that people place upon biodiversity in rural and urban areas. To investigate this, we will use the approach of Study Circles (a non-formal community learning approach) to engage a group of adults in each chosen location who will meet regularly during the experiment. We expect that results from the social experiment will induce a transformative change in values regarding biodiversity and will help to counteract biodiversity loss.

1.2. Why run and participate in a SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiment?

- Opportunity to contribute to the local implementation of the GREEN DEAL priorities
- Create and strengthen relationships with your community and local institutions
- Benefit from learning outcomes that can be adopted as part of your or your local stakeholders' own processes
- Together with others across Europe, collectively address a social issue and act to achieve its transformation

1.3 When should the social experiments start and for how long should they run?

Social experiments should last around 12 months and will start between April and June 2023.

1.4 What is the available budget and how many experiments will be funded? What are the eligible cost categories?

In the period between 2023 and 2024, SHARED GREEN DEAL will grant a total of EUR 528,000 to fund 24 social experiments, with a duration of 12 months.

We consider that applications requesting up to EUR 22000 would allow this experiment to be addressed appropriately. Nonetheless, this does not preclude submission and selection of proposals requesting other amounts.

Therefore, each social experiment can be allocated a budget of approximately EUR 22,000. HOWEVER, the exact amount may vary depending on local costs and the budget needed must be specified and justified by the applicants in the application form.

Applicants may submit proposals that exceed EUR 22,000 (up to a maximum of EUR 24,000); however, in this case, applicants might have to co-finance the missing amount.

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Successful applicants will sign a contract agreement and be awarded 30% of the budget upon signing the contract. The remaining amount will be transferred via an interim payment of 30% of the budget in Month 6 of the contract (after the approval of the interim report), whereas the final payment of 40% of the budget will be transferred upon completion of the work, as approved by the SHARED GREEN DEAL responsible partners and the European Commission.

Eligible cost categories:

- Human resources
- Travel costs for essential and justified travels
- Logistic costs connected to the organisation of events (e.g. rent of venues, catering)
- Communication costs (e.g. promotional materials, translation)
- Equipment
- Subcontracting - Justified outsourced activities (e.g. specific facilitation or technical assistance).

1.5 In what language should the social experiments be run?

Social experiments will be run in your local language.

However, to ensure that participants gain the most and ensure successful cooperation and exchange among the 24 social experiments, and in order that local partners are able to use resources provided by the central SHARED GREEN DEAL team, the applicant's main contact person is required to have at least level B1 command of English (please see section on eligibility below).

In addition, we require interview data collected from the experiment to be translated by the applicant into English.

1.6 What are the eligibility criteria?

1.6.1 Which applicants are eligible?

Proposals can be submitted only by singular organisations, consortia are not accepted; however it is possible to name local organisations who would like to be involved in the experiment activities.

To be eligible for the SHARED GREEN DEAL Grant, applicants must comply with all the following conditions:

- Be located in the European Union or Horizon2020 Associated countries (*note: UK based applicants ARE eligible under the current call*).
- The applicants must be either:
 - Local and regional authorities (including municipalities, cities, towns, villages *and* their local municipally owned companies and agencies)
 - Not-for-profit organisations (e.g. NGOs, civil society organisations, associations etc).
- *Please note: Universities / research organisations are not eligible to submit proposals. However they can be named as an organisation who would like to be involved in experiment activities led by an NGO or municipality. (this information was further clarified on 8 December 2022)*
- *Please note that ONLY for the Sustainable Mobility stream, eligible applicants should run the social experiments linked to locations with a minimum population size of 50.000 inhabitants.*
- Financial capacity - Applicants must have stable and sufficient resources to successfully implement their local social experiment.
- Applicants need to commit to provide the necessary human resources and skill to carry out the social experiments.
- The applicant's main contact persons are required to have at least level B1 command of English.

1.6.2 What are the exclusion criteria?

Applicants who are subject to an EU exclusion decision or in one of the following exclusion situations that bar them from receiving EU funding CANNOT participate:

- bankruptcy, winding up, affairs administered by the courts, arrangement with creditors, suspended business activities or other similar procedures (including procedures for persons with unlimited liability for the applicant's debts)
- in breach of social security or tax obligations (including if done by persons with unlimited liability for the applicant's debts)
- guilty of grave professional misconduct¹ (including if done by persons having powers of representation, decision-making or control, beneficial owners or persons who are essential for the award/implementation of the grant)
- committed fraud, corruption, links to a criminal organisation, money laundering, terrorism-related crimes (including terrorism financing), child labour or human trafficking (including if done by persons having powers of representation, decision-making or control, beneficial owners or persons who are essential for the award/implementation of the grant)
- shown significant deficiencies in complying with main obligations under an EU procurement contract, grant agreement, prize, expert contract, or similar (including if done by persons having powers of representation, decision-making or control, beneficial owners or persons who are essential for the award/implementation of the grant)
- guilty of irregularities within the meaning of Article 1(2) of Regulation No 2988/95 (including if done by persons having powers of representation, decision-making or control, beneficial owners or persons who are essential for the award/implementation of the grant)
- created under a different jurisdiction with the intent to circumvent fiscal, social or other legal obligations in the country of origin or created another entity with this purpose (including if done by persons having powers of representation, decision-making or control, beneficial owners or persons who are essential for the award/implementation of the grant).

Applicants will also be refused if it turns out that²:

- during the award procedure they misrepresented information required as a condition for participating or failed to supply that information.
- they were previously involved in the preparation of the current call for social experiments and this entails a distortion of competition that cannot be remedied otherwise (conflict of interest).
- The activity to be supported is already funded by another EU programme.

1.6.3 What are the desirable criteria (that are a plus)?

- Prior experience of running participatory community events and facilitation skills to run co-creation processes.
- Demonstrable capacity to recruit participants and keep them actively involved.
- Prior experience in conducting interviews.
- A letter of support signed by a political representative of the local/regional authority on which territory the social experiment takes place. This is applicable only to applicants who are not-for-profit organisations or local municipally owned companies and agencies.

¹ Professional misconduct includes: violation of ethical standards of the profession, wrongful conduct with impact on professional credibility, false declarations/misrepresentation of information, participation in a cartel or other agreement distorting competition, violation of IPR, attempting to influence decision-making processes or obtain confidential information from public authorities to gain advantage.

² See Article 141 EU Financial Regulation 2018/1046 (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32018R1046&qid=15350460240120>)

1.7 What do you commit to?

1.7.1 What are the overall commitments you need to comply with concerning the call (applicable to all social experiment streams)?

- Attend 12 online progress meetings (1/month) to update your SHARED GREEN DEAL contact partner on your latest activities and progress. This involves responding to a brief monthly progress survey pre-meeting.
- Participate in an in-person 1,5-days training linked to your experiment stream (in English) in April 2023 - travel and accommodation costs will be reimbursed via an additional budget provided by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project for 1 person from your organization, based on real costs (proof via invoices will be required)
- Depending on the experiment stream you apply under, you need to commit to the following training dates (*please note you might need to travel on the day prior to the training*):
 - Clean Energy: Place: Vienna, Austria; Date: 26-27 April 2023
 - Circular Economy: Place: Larnaca, Cyprus; Date: 27-28 April 2023
 - Efficient Renovations: Place: Cambridge, UK; Date: 25-26 April 2023
 - Sustainable Mobility: Place: Vienna, Austria; Date: 4-5 April 2023
 - Sustainable Food: Place: Rotterdam, the Netherlands; Date: 12-13 April 2023
 - Preserving Biodiversity: Place: Ljubljana, Slovenia, 25-26 April 2023
- Participate in a in-person 1,5 days study tour within the field of your social experiment in late 2023 or early 2024 (precise dates to be confirmed at a later stage) - travel and accommodation costs will be reimbursed via an additional budget provided by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project for 1 person from your organization (proof based on invoices will be required). *Please note the study tours are different from the training mentioned above.*
- Host the above-mentioned study tour (ONLY if you apply to be a lighthouse local partner via the application form and are selected for this). In this case, logistics (e.g. catering, renting of room etc) will be covered by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project (please note this should include organizing 3 meals for 10 participants).
- Undertake 10 in-depth interviews with the local target stakeholders and citizens of the social experiment INCLUDING translating the questions from English into your local language and the answers into English. Interview resources and transcripts will be provided by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.
- Provide relevant information on the events held (date, title, photos etc). Event resources will be provided.
- Participate in a webinar to share your learnings and experiences within your local social experiment at the end of the experiment.

1.7.2 What are the commitments per each specific social experiment stream?

In addition, as each social experiment stream is different, your commitment varies depending on the stream.

Clean Energy: You will need to commit to:

- Organise 4 stakeholder-focused co-creation events of approx. 3 hours with approximately 20 attendees invited to each event. The focus of the events is on imagining the energy future of your area by involving various groups of stakeholders: the first meeting should involve attendees representing government/policy makers, the second meeting should involve civil society

organisations, the third meeting should involve local businesses and public and private businesses, the fourth meeting should involve residents in the area.

- Organise a joint stakeholder group event gathering representatives of the 4 stakeholder-focused co-creation events (with more than 60 participants) to share potential future scenarios, enable an exchange of visions, barriers and enablers for a successful and locally-appropriate energy transition.
- Produce reflections, feedback, recommendations, and next steps and communicate these to all attendees of the events.

Please note that concerning the target group there is an aim to engage younger people (18-30) and older generations (+65) to reflect the intergenerational focus of the social experiment.

For further details, please go to the experiment webpage.

Circular Economy: You will need to commit to:

- Set up a Local Accelerator Hub (LAH) as an online platform (which can be hosted on an existing website) serving as a one-stop source on circular business innovation with the role of collecting knowledge and linking relevant stakeholders. The thematic field of the LAH should be defined by the applicant in the application form (in line with the resource-intensive sectors identified within the EU Circular Economy Action Plan: 1. packaging, 2. textiles, 3. plastics, 4. batteries and vehicles, 5. electronics and ICT, 6. construction and buildings, 7. food, water and nutrients). The LAH should gather more than 10 local businesses as active participants of the platform (e.g., local producers, local retailers), local business organisations (e.g. retailers' associations), consumer' associations, associations for disabled citizens (e.g. visually and mobility impaired), local authorities, financial institutions, etc. Other actors with complementary roles should be included (e.g. local government, research and academic organisations, NGOs).
- Organise three workshops:
 - Workshop 1: a circular business innovation workshop to map current practices and identify good practices
 - Two local design thinking workshops focused on business innovation linked to the thematic field of action of your LAH. The workshops need to involve local businesses and consumers:
 - Workshop 2: problem setting - define a circularity target linked to new products or services creation or problems from the greater community. Identification and development of common local circular business solutions. (with involvement from local businesses).
 - Workshop 3: user focus approach - identify core user needs and behaviours, detect the relevance of the solutions regarding circular innovation and help translate them into design criteria. Collect consumer feedback on potential local circular business solutions.
- Build the knowledge repository of the LAH by identifying at least 25 good practices or existing local programmes and initiatives in the focus field of the LAH linked to circular business innovations.
- Attend two virtual meetings to share your best practices and learn from examples identified within other social experiments in other countries
- Organise a local circular business award aiming to highlight the best ideas of the local businesses registered in the LAH to incorporate sustainable circular economy in their business models.

Please note that concerning the target group there is an aim to include the needs of disabled customers as part of fostering feedback loops in the innovation process.

Efficient Renovations: You will need to commit to:

- Set up a local knowledge network involving at least 30 participants/members with approximately 50:50 balance of professionals and citizens. Engage at least 10 households at risk of energy poverty as participants; at least 10 representatives of SMEs in the green jobs sector as well as other relevant professionals (e.g. local authorities; housing associations; social workers; health organisations, energy agencies, energy communities, local groups with a focus on energy poverty); and at least 1 provider of funding for renovation. Aim to engage at least 60% female participants.
- Host five capacity-building activities to share knowledge and skills, with at least 10+ participants at each activity:
 - Activity 1 will focus on meeting members of the network, discussing past renovation experiences, future renovation priorities, discuss motivation and shape the following activities together. Duration: 3 hours
 - Activity 2 will focus on experiencing the results of others who have been frontrunners in energy efficient renovations. A series of ‘eco-home tours’ will be organised, where participants can e.g. witness for themselves the results of recent renovations, ask for advice etc. It could even include visiting a construction site where a major renovation is currently underway. We anticipate that both the visitors and hosts will be members of the local knowledge network. *Duration:* 60-90minutes per tour, with around 3-5 tours organised. Participants of the local knowledge network must go to at least one tour.
 - Activity 3 will focus on site visits of pre-renovation projects of the members of the knowledge network. These should be interactive and practical visits, with tangible links made to the evolving renovation plans, with specific advisory discussions (e.g. a pre-renovation site visit, where knowledge network members could discuss and debate first steps for renovation). *Duration:* 60-90minutes per tour, with around 3-5 tours organised. Participants of the local knowledge network must go to at least one site visit.
 - Activity 4 will focus on connecting to existing local programmes and initiatives, to help ensure longer-term legacies. Gather contributions and feedback to be fed into a toolkit. Duration: 3 hours.
 - Activity 5 will focus on what has been learnt throughout the experiment, and what next steps may entail (both as individuals and what they may like from municipalities and NGOs). A prompt for discussion will be a locally focused toolkit, which will have been produced collectively by the 4 social experiment locations that will be selected for this stream of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project. Network members will reflect on this toolkit and their proposed changes will be considered in the final version of the toolkit. *Duration:* 3 hours.

Please note that concerning the target group there is an aim to engage at least 60% female members in the knowledge network.

Also note that each local partner will take responsibility for creating a network that is focused on one of the following four renovation contexts: residential urban energy poverty; residential rural energy poverty; care homes; schools.

Sustainable Mobility: You will need to commit to:

- Involve three primary and/or secondary schools in the experiment (you need to provide a signed letter of interest by each of the three schools in the application form)
- Set up an urban mobility lab for smart and sustainable mobility in the context of schools. The lab should involve 30 young people (ages 10-16) from three different schools and 5-10 other stakeholders (e.g., teachers, parents, members of school administration, district/city administration/departments, mobility providers, etc.).

- Work together in a co-creative setting in the form of “local mobility future forums” which will meet eight times using age-appropriate, playful approaches (e.g., excursions, games, online tools, workshops). These are envisaged to include:
 - A first forum with the 5-10 adult participants, including identification of committee members
 - A first forum with the 30 student participants, including identification of committee members
 - One committee member only meeting
 - Four fora for all participants to: (i) identify fields of action, (ii) propose initial policy ideas, (iii) design context-specific solutions, (iv) finalise solutions.
 - A final forum event which is open more widely at which ideas and recommendations are presented
- The mobility lab will formulate, on the one hand, policy recommendations for travel to school strategies at the city level and thereby foster the representation of young people in policy making and planning processes. On the other hand, each mobility lab will co-create context-specific solutions, understood as interventions to disrupt and develop institutionalised behaviour and norms (e.g., games, exhibitions, info boxes, educational material, small physical interventions with potential for infrastructure-related interventions etc.), to raise awareness of smart and sustainable school mobility.

Please note that concerning the target group there is an aim to engage at least 30 young people in local planning processes concerning school mobility.

Sustainable Food: You will need to commit to:

- Recruit 5-10 (*note: an earlier version of this document said 15-20 but 5-10 is the correct number*) local food system change makers. *By change makers we mean inspiring people with different backgrounds that operate at the grassroots level, who are undertaking actions and organising activities to create awareness and make (small) changes within the food system.*
- Host and facilitate 4 meetings that build on transition governance methods for the local food system change makers to work towards an action agenda. SHARED GREEN DEAL partners will support you in applying these methods.
 - Meeting 1 will focus on co-creative, shared problem structuring including descriptions of needs and barriers for local food system transition as well as expressing ideas for future alternatives.
 - Meeting 2 will focus on approving and prioritising the problems, needs and ideas collected in Meeting 1. In addition, participants will co-create a shared future vision of a sustainable and healthy local food system in form of an alternative narrative, combined with a set of priority innovations to be implemented/tested to move towards achieving this vision.
 - Meeting 3 will focus on presenting synthesis of future narratives and principles of sustainable, healthy food system. Identifying a set of context specific actions and activating engagements to experiment with solutions for accelerating food system transitions. Designing concrete pilot actions and identifying requirements for their implementation.
 - In addition, around the full Meetings 1-3 it is envisaged that a subset of the group (the ‘transition committee’) would provide additional feedback on the process.
 - Meeting 4: a virtual reflexive learning & outreach assembly (one or two sessions) will focus on identifying key learnings, lessons learned and recommendations across all four food experiment locations.

Please note that concerning the target group there is an aim to engage young participants in the network of local food system change makers so that one third of the network members are young participants (age 18 - 35).

Preserving Biodiversity: You will need to commit to:

- Recruit around 10-15 adults
- Co-design an adult education programme based on the Study Circle approach focused on reinforcing existing values or change in values regarding biodiversity. This will be done via proactive involvement of participants through a series of meetings to:
 - Identify their interest in biodiversity, define goals and make a learning plan (what interests the participants, finding a cross-section of interests)
 - Set goals more precisely (What do participants already know about biodiversity?; What values do they have related to biodiversity?; What do they want to learn more about biodiversity?; an example could be what is biodiversity in my local environment) and setting the action goals (how are participants going to transfer new knowledge and values, and share them with the local environment; for example an exhibition, a round table discussion, a new walking trail, a brochure, set of postcards, etc.)
 - Decide whether participants want to invite an expert to speak on the topic and who they would like to invite. Potential visit and presentation by biodiversity expert(s)
- Organise a final public event (format to be defined by the participants involved in the learning programme – for example a round table discussion, presentation of a brochure, opening a new walking trail, etc.) publicly showing to the local community what was learnt during the social experiment

Please note that concerning the target group there is an aim to engage adults who may have experienced isolation (e.g. during the pandemic).

2. Application Process

2.1 When to apply?

The present Call for applications will stay open from **25.11.2022 until 31.01.2023 at 23.59 CET (note - this was added following questions on the specific timing)**. No applications will be accepted after this date.

Applicants can submit their proposal at any time within this timeframe.

The assessment and evaluation of applications will take approximately 1 month following the call deadline.

2.2. How can I access the application forms?

Interested applicants need to first register and then fill in an online application form.

To access the form, please [register here](#), and include the following information:

- Name
- Organisation
- Organisation type
 - Local and regional authority (including municipalities, cities, towns, villages *and* their local municipally owned companies and agencies)

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- Not-for-profit organisation (e.g. NGOs, civil society organisations, associations etc).
- Country
- Email
- Stream of interest: *please select among the 6 streams in the list*

Thereafter, you will receive an email with the link to the full application form of the social experiment stream you expressed interest in: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, Preserving Biodiversity.

After submission, you will receive a confirmation email to the email address provided in the application. In case you do not receive such confirmation, please contact info@sharedgreendeal.eu

2.3 How to submit an application? What information is required?

The application process will happen in one step.

All proposals must be submitted online using the relevant application forms (please consult section “2.2. How can I access the application forms?”). Paper applications are NOT accepted.

Application forms are divided in three parts:

Part A: Contact details and administrative information of the applicant organisation

Part B: Detailed description of your local social experiment

Part C: Human and financial resources

Annexes (to be uploaded) – Budget file, Letter of support in case applicable and relevant

2.4 What are the Evaluation Criteria?

Applications will be assessed and evaluated according to the following criteria.

Relevance: Scope, objectives, impact: 40 POINTS		
Problem analysis and quality of the approach to address the described problem	The local needs and barriers and link to the actions and the way they tackle the barriers are clear and reasonable	15 points
The target group is clearly defined and is/will be appropriately engaged	The target group is clearly defined and suitably chosen in line with the need and action as well as the engagement strategy. The engagement strategy includes specific actions to ensure appropriate representation and participation of all genders and of groups who are in a vulnerable position (according to the experiment target group) in the social experiment.	10 points
Link to existing local/European initiatives	Clear and proved connection,	15 points

	building synergies with existing local policies, projects and initiatives. The project avoids duplication with projects funded by Union programmes	
Quality: Actions, allocation of resources: 30 POINTS		
Is the Action Clear and consistent?	A scale from 1 to 5 where 5 = everything is clear, with timeline, main milestones indicated, deliverables included, baseline and target value clearly stated	20 points
Allocation of resources and skills	The applicant has sufficient resources and capacity to implement the social experiment Efficient use of resources	10 points
Impact: expected results and visibility: 30 POINTS		
Communication	Activities to increase visibility (use of social media, production of comms material etc), no. of persons reached, diversity of stakeholders reached	10 points
Results	How appropriate are the expected results of the social experiments	10 points
Outreach	Outreach (engagement in an active way – not communication)	10 points

Please note that in addition to the above-mentioned evaluation criteria, the SHARED GREEN DEAL project needs to select the 4 social experiment locations under each of the 6 SHARED GREEN DEAL streams, in accordance with:

- geographical balance between Northern, Eastern, Southern, and Western Europe
- balance between type of applicants:
 - Local and regional authorities (including municipalities, cities, towns, villages *and* their local municipally owned companies and agencies)
 - Not-for-profit organisations (e.g. NGOs, civil society organisations, associations etc).
- balance between urban/peri-urban/rural locations

2.5 When and how applicants will be informed of the results?

The assessment and evaluation of applications will take approximately 1 month after the call deadline.

Applicants will be notified mid-March via the main contact's email address provided in the application form.

3. What is the legal and financial set-up of the Grant Agreements

Selected applicants will have to sign a contract, which will set the framework for the grant and its terms and conditions, in particular concerning deliverables, reporting and payments. The contract will include information regarding:

- The social experiment starting date and duration.
- Milestones and deliverables
- Form of grant, funding rate and maximum grant amount
- Budget categories and cost eligibility rules
- Reporting and payment arrangements

4. What are the payment arrangements?

Payment will follow the signature of the Grant Agreement by beneficiaries and representatives of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, and after clearance from the European Commission.

Payment will be arranged in three tranches:

- A pre-financing of 30% with the signature of the partnership agreement
- An interim payment (in Month 6, mid-way through the social experiment) – **upon request by applicant upon submission of the interim report (please see section on Reporting below)**
- The remaining 40% will be provided upon approval of the final report
- Project activities must be implemented by the beneficiaries within 12 months.

5. What does reporting consist of?

All projects will have to submit a final narrative and financial report within 30 days after the last day of the social experiment, including annexes (12 sets of field notes, translations of 10 interviews, summary of the social experiment, links to any relevant websites, photos taken in events related to the social experiment if applicable).

Reporting templates will be made available soon on the SHARED GREEN DEAL project website.

A progress report will be submitted in Month 6 of the local social experiment.

Monthly online meetings (1-2 hours) will be organised with the SHARED GREEN DEAL project representatives.

6. What are the communication obligations?

All project outputs and deliverables will have to display the logo of SHARED GREEN DEAL and of the European Commission.

All local partners will need to inform the SHARED GREEN DEAL contacts about their local public events and promote them via the SHARED GREEN DEAL communication channels.

The following disclaimer, accompanied by the EU flag, should be used on all public material produced by your social experiment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101036640. The sole responsibility for this content lies with the SHARED GREEN DEAL project and does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

7. Data and privacy policy

SHARED GREEN DEAL Partner, Energy Cities, will store the application forms and process personal data that applicants will supply therein. Personal data will be held for a maximum of 3 years after the end of the project (i.e. up to 31 Jan 2030), after which time it will be destroyed.

Please note that during this period, the application forms might be shared with the European Commission.

8. Who should I contact?

Should you have any queries linked to the application process, please contact info@sharedgreendeal.eu

Should you have queries about any specific SHARED GREEN DEAL stream, please indicate this in the subject line of your email.

9. Questions received by email and their answers

- **Is it possible to submit applications to more than one stream?**
Yes. Please note you need to commit to provide the necessary human resources and skill to carry out both social experiments in case you are selected for both streams. You will need to submit separate application forms for each stream of interest. Please note that, even though there are administrative similarities between the forms, the content you need to provide is different since the activities in each stream are different. You will receive the links to the full application forms after confirming interest here: https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=5CrhDfdSfUOIDhi98UDefulbWnOn9_JEiYDY9h5sd2IUOFdVUVFUS1VBQIBJVTFCOExpNFRDSzBJTi4u.
- **Can we match the funding with funding from another source?**
Yes, you can propose to use funding from another source in addition to SHARED GREEN DEAL funding, in your plans. It is important to have a clear and proven connection, build synergies with existing local policies, projects and initiatives. However, you need to ensure that you avoid duplication with projects funded by European Union programmes. Therefore, yes, you can match the funding, however you need to clearly show the added value of the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment and to show that it is funding complementary and additional activities to the ones already funded. See also section 1.6.2.
- **Would there be a possibility to apply the biodiversity theme among governmental buildings (green roofs) and employees rather than in the city?**
We are open to applicants tailoring the experiment plans to their own contexts but there are a few factors to bear in mind. For example, in the application form for the biodiversity stream it asks you to describe if/how your context relates to (i) rural protected landscapes and/or (ii) urban green spaces and/or (iii) rural cultural landscapes. In addition, it is important to address how the target audience will be reached, which will be taken into account in the scoring of each proposal. As with all streams, please refer to the commitments per stream (see section 1.7.2) and the guidelines on the specific scoring criteria (see section 2.4).
- **Can we submit as an organisation based in academia instead of as an NGO?**
No, universities and research centres are not eligible to submit applications. However, universities/research centres can be named as organisations who would like to be involved

in experiment activities led by an NGO or municipality, and successful eligible applicants might subcontract specific tasks to academic partners. See also section 1.6.1.

- **Are subsistence (or other) costs covered by the project for the two trips funded directly by SHARED GREEN DEAL outside the scope of the 22.000 Euro?**
Only the travel (i.e. train tickets etc.) and the accommodation (i.e. Hotel) is covered directly by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project outside the scope of the experiment funding. However, certain meals will be organised during the programme of the training and the study tours and those will be covered directly by the organisers.
- **Can the 10 local businesses (required in the Circular Economy Stream) include organizations that are not for profit, for example waste and recycling associations?**
The objective is to connect with the local business community and in the cases where this includes organisations not working towards profit, this is acceptable.
- **Can a cluster of neighboring towns (smaller towns centered around a bigger one) that overall surpass the 50.000 inhabitants mark be considered or does it need to be one single administrative unit that fulfills the criteria (Mobility Stream)?**
The mobility stream focuses on individual cities, so your application should include only one city (a single administrative unit) as an experiment location.
- **Is the question "How will you communicate and disseminate your local social experiment?" related to the 12 months implementation period of after?**
This is primarily related to the project period. Commitments for activities after the 12 months implementation can also be included (and will be viewed favorably). A question on how you will use the project outputs is also included, in which further communication activities could be relevant.
- **Can I apply as an individual based in a research institute? If not, can our regional chamber of commerce submit the application?**
Applying as an individual is not possible. If the Regional Chamber of Commerce is non profit it can submit the application.
- **Is it allowed to pay participants of the workshops through the grant?**
Yes, that is possible.
- **Information on Annual Turnover is requested for 2021 but we are a new organisation. What should we do?**
You are eligible to apply, as not having an annual turnover 2021 is not a problem on its own. The question is part of a series of questions for us to reflect on your organisation and the capability you would have to deploy the experiment. No turnover is not an issue if you can show you have the necessary financial capacity through the other questions.
- **Are the actions to be implemented are only those indicated in 1.7.1. and 1.7.2 or can we develop a social project beyond those indications.**
You need to commit to implement the actions listed under 1.7.1 and 1.7.2, however we encourage you to tailor them to your local needs and in case you need to add additional tasks to make a coherent local social experiment, please feel free to do so. Indeed, the most important is to carry out a meaningful social experiment locally. In addition, the budget template that you need to submit was developed to allow you to do so, therefore you can add in other activities and cost categories, as long as your budget claim remains reasonably within EUR 22,000. Note that applicants may exceed this amount (up to a maximum of EUR 24,000); however, in this case, applicants might have to co-finance the missing amount. Please consult Section 1.4 for more details.

- **Does the application or the reporting require documents attesting to the allocation of resources to cover the project costs?**
A budget is requested in the application. The more details in this the better.
- **Can you submit two proposals in the same stream?**
No, this is not possible. Each evaluation takes time for us and each application takes time for you. We therefore request only one application in each stream per lead partner.
- **When does the call close?**
At 23.59 CET on January 31, 2023. We strongly recommend to not wait until the final moments. ,
- **Will the Application deadline be extended?**
 - No, that is not our plan.
- **I have not received the application form after confirming my interest.**
 - Please see below for the direct links (note: updated on 28/1/2023 when we viewed the coordination of interest to be complete)
 - Clean Energy :
<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Clean-Energy-SHARED-GREEN-DEAL>
 - Efficient Renovations :
<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Efficient-Renovations-SHARED-GREEN-DEAL>
 - Circular Economy:
<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Circular-Economy-SHARED-GREEN-DEAL>
 - Sustainable Mobility :
<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Sustainable-Mobility-SHARED-GREEN-DEAL>
 - Sustainable Food:
<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Sustainable-Food-SHARED-GREEN-DEAL>
 - Preserving Biodiversity:
<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/Preserving-Biodiversity-SHARED-GREEN-DEAL>
- **Do you have an example of a Letter of Support**
 - We do not, but we have a draft template you can use [here](#). Please note this style is an example. The style is not a requirement.

Questions received during Q&A Session and their answers

Using the search function is recommended for the below.

General Questions		
Questions	Answers	
1	Is it necessary to fully translate the Letters of	It is enough to show the author

	support in EN or we just have to show the author and to present a summary of the content?	and do a summary. Please do not forget to attach the signed letter in your language in addition to the summary.
2	If we start in June 2023, we can end in May 2024 ?	Yes, you can.
3	Do associations have to be registered in the national non-profit register to be eligible?	Organisations applying should be officially recognized as non-for-profit.
4	Are county councils eligible?	Yes, they are.
5	Registered yesterday but have not received an application yet. Will it take a 1-2 day to be sent or should we re-register?	Send an email to info@sharedgreendeal.eu and we will sort it out.
6	Are applications individual?	Yes, it is only possible to submit a proposal as an individual applicant and not as consortium, but you can identify possible partners already in the proposal.
7	Can an not-for-profit organisation based in the UK apply to run an experiment in another EU country where it has staff and relevant networks?	Yes, it can.
8	Can one NGO present more than one proposal?	You can present proposals for different streams, but one organisation cannot apply several times for the same stream.
9	What does "Lighthouse" refer to?	One partner in each stream. This partner will (most notably) be the host of the Study visit (with organisation support from the project), logistics costs of this study tour will be funded from an additional budget, directly by SHARED GREEN DEAL.
10	Are energy cooperatives eligible?	Yes, they are.
11	Can an organisation (e.g. an energy cooperative) functioning only with volunteers apply?	Yes, however it will be necessary to show that it has the human resources required to carry out the experiment.
12	In the budget, where to add expendable materials? Equipment perhaps?	In the application form, you can download the budget file with the different categories. Indeed it should be under equipment
13	Do we have to attach any document to justify the needed language requirement?	No, a formal document is not necessary.
14	As our organization is newly founded, how do you define stable and sufficient financial resources?	You are eligible to apply, as not having an annual turnover 2021 is not a problem on its own. The question is part of a series of questions for us to reflect on your organisation and the capability

		you would have to deploy the experiment. No turnover is not an issue if you can show you have the necessary financial capacity through the other questions.
15	When you say "provide relevant info on the events held" - do you have a template with what you'd like to receive that qualifies as required information? Are these reports? Questionnaires that are filled in online like the application survey?	Linked to events, we'd like to receive prior data to promote and show the event on the SHARED GREEN DEAL website when relevant (date, title, programme). Post event, you will need to share (photos, summary of findings - 1-2 pages, date, title, programme, anycomms material produced etc).
16	The costs related to human resources are the staff costs of 1 person?	No, it can be for more than 1 person.
17	How and where do we apply for the streams?	You confirm your interest here and you will then receive the direct submission info, including the link to the full application form, for your desired streams: https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=5CrhDfdSfUOIDhi98UDefulbWnOn9_JEiYDY9h5sd2IUOFdVUVFUS1VBQIBJVTFCOExPNFRDSzBJTi4u
18	Is there budget planned for project controlling?	Central project coordination and administration time would need to be included within your 22k budget.
19	Is it possible to apply as a Regional Agency (Maribor) for more than one area?	It is fine to submit more than one application across the experiment streams (e.g. both renovations and circular economy), but we would ask that a maximum of one application is submitted per organisation for each experiment stream (e.g. pick your best 'area' in your region for the food experiment and only submit that one). After all, we can only select one location for each of North/South/East/West in Europe, and so you'd be in competition with yourself instantly.
20	What are the requirements for the financial reporting? What documents do we need to provide?	A template for the financial report will be provided (not yet available) with a list of supporting documents. It will be similar to what is necessary for Horizon Europe programme's financial reports (mainly invoices).
21	Are you planning to launch a similar new call in 2024?	Unfortunately no other call is planned in 2024. This is a one-time opportunity - at least only envisioned as such at this stage.
22	What kind of costs should be included in "justified outsourced activities" (7th point in budget)? Does this mean that costs in points 1-6 from the budget cannot be outsourced?	The type of costs depends on the experiment, but indeed all subcontracting costs should be listed under subcontracting.
23	Can an external consultant represent the NGO at training dates etc. If NGO staff do not have the required English level?	It is possible to have an external consultant represent the association in the international meetings; however, in this case, the consultant needs to be part of the local implementation team, so

		that the person can properly represent the organization and give feedback, progress update, take back and apply the relevant information and learnings from the training etc. Please note that in addition to the site visit and the study tour, the person needs to also attend 12 update meetings (once / month for approximately 1-2 hours) and provide information, reports and annexes in English.
24	Can the local authority represent at study tour and training day the involved NGO or external expert in case she/he doesn't speak at the required English level?	The training is intended to ensure that the people leading the experiments get familiar with our methods, way of working and get to know the team. So it is important that the person attending the training, is also the person most involved in organising the experiments.
25	We were thinking to involve in our project as a target group the representatives of the different neighbourhoods in Lisbon. This could ensure a positive spread of the social experiment results within the different parts of the city. Because we are addressing the decision-making level, we cannot control the inclusiveness. Should we change target group?	You need to build a coherent and meaningful local social experiment within the framework of the call. Depending on the different streams, different target groups need to be involved. Make sure that you ensure the inclusiveness by compensating with participants from another target group for instance.
26	Is there any model for the support letters?	There is no specific template to be used. Feel free to provide a personalised letter showing the relevance of the social experiment to you locally. However, if you need an example I'll be happy to provide it if you send an email to info@sharedgreendeal.eu .
27	Is it possible to also account for monetary compensation for participants' engagement in the social experiments?	Yes, this is eligible within the budget.
28	The project will provide extra funding to cover travel and accommodation costs for trainings and study tour. Does that mean that we don't need to put that costs into the application's budget?	Exactly. These costs will be refunded to you and are not included in the budget for running the experiment.
29	The "Is the Action Clear and consistent"" section of the evaluation criteria emphasises the need for a clear presentation of milestones, deliverables, indicators, but there is no direct question on this in the application form. How do we align the set of questions and the evaluation system?	The timeline and the material produced should be clear from the description of the different sections of the form. You should also emphasize if there are specific deliverables (for instance on communication, such as brochure, publication etc, any specific additional actions needed for your experiment to tackle the needs and barriers addressed). Of course, this should be in line and consistent with the budget file.
30	Is there a possibility of having 2 people attending the trainings?	An extra person can join but, only one person will be funded from the additional budget on top of the grant. You will need to cover

		the expenditure of the additional person from your own funds.
31	<p>The deadline for the funding project at the end of January is very short for us.</p> <p>How complex are the application formalities? Will there be follow-up projects? Is this a beginning of a bigger project/follow up projects?</p>	<p>We hope it's not too complex.</p> <p>Essentially, if your desires fit with what we seek it shouldn't be long and there is no follow up projects required by you (or planned by us).</p> <p>Please register here to be invited to access the full application form(s).</p> <p>https://forms.office.com/Pages/ResponsePage.aspx?id=5CrhDfdSfUOIDhi98UDefulbWnOn9_JEiYDY9h5sd2IUOFdVUVFUS1VBQIBJVTFCOExpNFRDSzBJTi4u</p>
32	<p>About stakeholders: Can a stakeholder be a programme implementer that is subcontracted to the project too, if the stakeholder would be important in sharing experiences of learning and generating innovative programme ideas as well?</p>	<p>Yes stakeholders can implement a part of the project, however subcontracting should be reasonable (not everything should be subcontracted).</p>
33	<p>If we decide to be "the lighthouse" location what other activities (beside organising and hosting the study tour we need to carry out?</p>	<p>As a light house case, you will carry out the same tasks as the other locations (so the interviews, the required activities by the stream, etc.). The difference with the other locations is that you are highlighted as a good example/source of inspiration in that particular field.</p>
34	<p>Can a freelance usually working with an NGO be included in the staff cost? or a sub-contract is needed to involve the expert?</p>	<p>It is staff cost if the expert is an in-house consultant, otherwise the expert should be subcontracted.</p>
35	<p>Is it acceptable if the required letter of support for a not-for-profit organisation is issued by a Chamber of Commerce as a local authority?</p>	<p>No, a Chamber of Commerce is not considered as a local authority. The signatory of the letter should be a local or regional government.</p>
36	<p>In the table on the evaluation criteria, the clarity of the action is evaluated. Since the action seems to be limited to the organisation of the meetings, what is meant specifically?</p>	<p>We encourage you to tailor and adapt the social experiment to your local needs. This means that you can add in additional actions and events that might be relevant to build a coherent local social experiment. The budget file allows you flexibility to add these activities in. The clarity is important to see how the local needs link with solutions proposed and what potential deliverables could be useful locally (e.g. additional activities to the ones mentioned as compulsory).</p>
37	<p>In the budget template, shall we put details of the staff costs (e.g. put on separate lines the remunerations for Project manager, experts, accountant, etc...) or put the expenditure as a lump sum?</p>	<p>Staff costs should be put as lump sum in the budget template.</p>

38	For the letter of support can it be written in the local language and then translated ?	It can be written in local language but needs to be summarized in English. Please submit both versions.
39	The support letters should they be only from the local authorities or we can also send letters from other NGOs/local SMEs?	Only the local authority is required.
40	There is a primary and a secondary contact person that should be named on the application– can more people work on the project? For example, can I have a third or fourth colleague help for a workshop who is otherwise not involved and can they write their hours worked on the project, or can staff cost only cover the people who are listed within the application?	Feel free to set up a team working on the local social experiment. The contact persons listed in the form will be those to whom we will come back at the first stage to send the evaluation outcomes.
41	In the call is written that is possible to appoint co-partners, but just the main organization should submit a proposal. How and when can be appointed co-partners in the project? And is it possible to include their costs in the budget?	You can involve them as a subcontractor if relevant. In that case their costs should not be staff costs, but listed in the subcontracting category. Your organisation as contact/grant agreement signatory is responsible for the overall commitments in the contract.
42	Is a public education charity eligible to apply? Our organisation engages in research and public outreach concerning inequality, democracy, and climate justice in the current political, economic, and social environment.	You are eligible if you are a not-for-profit organisations (e.g. NGOs, civil society organisations, associations, etc.) and registered so.
43	Should the letter of support for NGOs also contain the Shared Green Deal logo, EU logo and disclaimer? And is it submitted with the online application form?	The logos are not necessary in the application phase. Yes, the letter is to be submitted in the online application form
44	I registered for one stream but I would like to change to a different stream, is that ok?	Just confirm your interest in the new stream and you should receive a new link.
45	In terms of duration, if an organisation has designed a social experiment that lasts two months for instance, can it repeat it with different participants in order to comply with the 1 year rule, or it has to expand the experiment to last more?	Each of the streams have scheduled their activities to fit a 1 year timeline. Not sure what stream you are talking about and how you envision to do this in (e.g.) 2 months. In general, all streams have taken into account the feasibility of the experiment into the timeline: so the extent of the engagement of the participants, and collection of the data. Please note that you need to comply with the overall requirements and the stream specific requirements, however you can adapt the

		experiment so that it answers your local needs.
46	Will the 22 partners of the Shared Green Deal provide any support to the local experimental partners or will they have any role to play in this call?	We hope to support you as much as possible - we have expert partners dedicated to each topic and in addition to that will promote your work, invite for events, share your efforts with the Commission and much, much more. The training sessions will be organised by the relevant SHARED GREEN DEAL partners.
47	About the letter of support signed by a political representative of the local/regional authority - does it need to be the highest authority present (like mayor) or is a member of the city council fine?	A signature from a member of the city/county council is fine.
48	As an NGO that did not conduct any other projects in the last 3 years, can I apply ?	Yes, you are eligible to apply.
49	Should the costs of performing tasks as a "lighthouse local partner" fit in the budget of the entire project or there are additional funds planned for this optional task? Where to place those costs in the budget?	You do not need to place those costs in the budget as these will be covered directly by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, in addition to the 22 000 euros dedicated to the local social experiment. In terms of costs, being a lighthouse implies hosting a study tour involving approximately 10 participants. The SHARED GREEN DEAL project will provide extra funding to cover the costs of the event (e.g. catering, renting of room etc).
50	Are we to include VAT where applicable when submitting the financial statement ?	Yes
51	Do you have any diagrams for summarizing the interaction methods with the public?	No
52	Where can we see existing experiments? Do we have to contact them to find synergies?	Each thematic area will be grouped and meet both for trainings and the study trip. Hopefully the beginning of strong connections.
53	Is it a problem if just one staff member is included in the budget table?	You will need to include a lump sum for the staff costs in the budget table.
54	What proportion of bids are anticipated from NGOs rather than local government agencies?	Ideally 50/50. Interest seems equally big from both groups until now.
55	There will be 1 training and 1 study tour that will be reimbursed via the additional budget? Or 2 trainings and 1 study tour? Are these costs included in the project's budget table (3. Travel costs) and part of the 22.000 EUR threshold?	1 in-person training and 1 in-person study tour will be reimbursed. We cover hotel and logistics with additional funding <u>on top</u> of the Grant for 1 person from the applicant organisation.

56	Do we get a formal letter of intent or we can form it freely?	Forming it freely is okay.
57	When we talk about ""Equipment"", which kind of cost are eligible? (sign posts, exhibition material,...)?	Yes, depending on what is relevant to build a coherent local social experiment. Please remember to justify those costs.
58	If there are savings during the project implementation - will it be possible to transfer these funds to other budget items? What is the procedure?	Yes, as long as they are justified and relevant to build a coherent social experiment in line with the initial objectives. You can justify this in the progress report of Month 6. In addition monthly progress meetings of 1-2 hours will be hold, so you can raise and discuss any issues within these meetings as well.
59	If a NGO applies to 2 different streams, can it win both of them, or only one? If it cannot win both, is it possible to prioritize?	Yes, an NGO can apply to two streams and win both.
60	Will it be possible to transfer costs between budget items within one task?	Yes
61	Are regional intelligent specializations (RIS) partnerships - while being not-for-profit - eligible to apply?	Eligible applicants must be local and regional authorities (including municipalities, cities, towns, villages and their local municipally owned companies and agencies) and not-for-profit organisations (e.g. NGOs, civil society organisations, associations, etc.).
62	What documents do we need to provide to attest the financial capacity of our association?	Please register to express interest in the call and thereafter you will be able to access the full application form with the required elements.
63	The Call for Proposals does not specify the level of detail required to describe the planned actions: do we have to present all the tested actions in the call or we can formulate them during implementation of the project in the frame of the co-creation processes.	The application is primarily about demonstrating your capacity to deliver the envisaged work, including your networks, experiences, explanations of your contexts, etc... The training events that we speak of (in April) will involve in-depth discussions on your planned work programme. The final plans will then be agreed between the core project partners and you as new local partners then. So, please feel free to provide any ideas you have, but don't worry about presenting a 100% final plan, because this will inevitably change.
64	Are indirect costs eligible?	Indirect costs can be included in staff costs.
65	Where do you see these social experiments going in the future? Collectively, what will they build towards?	The idea is that they help accelerate/support actions that help us achieve the EU Green Deal ambitions! On our website we have outlined how we view these ambitions per stream. Depending on the different streams, we hope to spark a range of experiments/innovative practices.
66	Are computers eligible under	No

	equipment?	
67	<p>Could you please tell us more about the letter of support. In your FAQs document, it's listed as a desirable criteria, and says ""A letter of support signed by a political representative of the local/regional authority on which territory the social experiment takes place. This is applicable only to applicants who are not-for-profit organisations or local municipally owned companies and agencies.""</p> <p>Does it need to be a representative of the city, or could it also be a waste authority? Also: is it actually mandatory or desirable (just to clarify)</p>	<p>Preferably from an elected representative.</p>
68	<p>About the budget we should send to apply for the call, this will be a plan, but maybe it will change during the project and the needs, do we have to justify this changes?</p>	<p>You can highlight these changes in the monthly progress meetings as well as in the progress report of Month 6.</p>
69	<p>When do we get the real application form? I have already sent the interest form.</p>	<p>You should have received a link automatically. If there are any problems, just get in touch by sending an email to info@sharedgreendeal.eu.</p>
70	<p>What if we don't have any turnover? We are an expert NGO, with the main aim of working on policy and writing recommendations to national decision makers.</p>	<p>You are eligible to apply, as not having an annual turnover 2021 is not a problem on its own. The question is part of a series of questions for us to reflect on your organisation and the capability you would have to deploy the experiment. No turnover is not an issue if you can show you have the necessary financial capacity through the other questions.</p>
71	<p>Is there a max rate for the subcontracting costs out of the total budget?</p>	<p>No, these should stay reasonable. Most of the staff costs should be for the applicant organisation's staff or in house consultant. The applicant should have the main ownership of the project.</p>
72	<p>How detailed should costs be in the budget? E.g., is it enough that we name ""Making videos"" or shall we specify what kind of videos, how many videos, how long they are?</p>	<p>You should be as specific as possible.</p>
73	<p>What is the minimum and maximum duration of the project?</p>	<p>The experiments to be implemented have a duration of 1 year.</p>
74	<p>Can we include the costs for an additional person to the on-site training in the budget?</p>	<p>No, this needs to be provided from your own funding sources.</p>

75	The guidelines and FAQ inform us that it is possible to pay participants of the workshops through the grant. Please confirm us this statement.	Confirmed.
76	I represent a NGO which carries out research activities, but we are not registered as research organization. Can we submit an application as frontrunner/leader?	Yes, you can.
77	Is it relevant to have additional LOI from other organisations as well?	If you deem it relevant for your future social experiment, feel free to collect some; however this is not a requirement for the application.
78	Can you get a letter of support from a local politician or should it be from the council?	You need to have a letter of support signed by the mayor or a local elected representative. The experiments are based around a geographical region - so for example within clean energy the advantage of having a letter of support from local council means that they might include the outcomes in future local planning processes, a politician might not be in the same position to take the ideas forward.
79	What do you mean by a 'lighthouse tour'?	Lighthouse location = a location that would be a good or inspiring example in the field of question. So a place that has moved from a more or less experimental phase, into a more mature organisation/initiative. The lighthouse location should host a study tour for approximately 10 participants. All costs related to it will be funded directly by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, on top of the grant for your social experiment.
80	Is a public education charity eligible to apply? We do research but we are technically an NGO.	Yes, NGOs are eligible to apply.
81	Shall we clearly enumerate the milestones and deliverables in the AF or the evaluators will deduct it from the texts that are quite limited?	You should mention them when relevant. Also in case you need specific budget to produce them, please make sure you include them in the budget file.
82	Due to a lot of questions and VERY short time between the webinar and the deadline could you please consider to postpone deadline.	Unfortunately the deadline cannot be postponed. But do not worry, the full application is not a huge undertaking!
83	Is the overhead of 25% (indirect costs) included in the budget?	You need to include staff costs and overheads as a lump sum in the budget file. This is included in the 22 000 EUR grant.
84	For each of the stream will you be aiming to have geographically balanced	Yes.

	representation in each stream?	
85	If there are still unanswered questions, can I send them by emails before the deadline?	Yes, send them to info@sharedgreendeal.eu.
86	How can we make binding participation agreement with 10 or even 12 year-old school students, which do not have event limited law ability?	Binding participation agreements apply only to adults (older than 18 year-old)
	Clean Energy	
	Questions	Answers
1	Should visions and scenario be focused on clean energy in general, or is it possible to focus on more specific aspects of clean energy?	Specific aspects will be tailored in conjunction with the local organisation - for some it might be a specific plan for a certain renewable energy, to some it might be about a region using less energy, for others it might be for example planning to transition away from coal based industry etc...
2	Is it required that participants in the social experiment be under 18 and over 65 years of age?	No, within the clean energy group most of the stakeholder groups will be drawn from all ages - for the residents stakeholders visioning workshop we would like to make sure we include 18-25 year olds and over 65 year old but it's a goal not a requirement.
3	In the case of Clean Energy, can the order of the four co-creation events be changed (e.g. civil society before policy makers?)	Yes the order of the first 4 events is flexible, they could be all carried out in a one week period or over a few months - depending on what works best for the lead organisation - also in certain locations it may make sense to merge one or two visioning events - for example in a smaller country/region it might be logical to hold one event with policy makers and CSOs in one workshop.
4	Is it possible to submit a project that is based on accompany and empower people with workshops and a coaching offer?	If that empowerment fits with the requirements of the energy stream, it will be possible. (i.e. through the 4 stakeholders workshops etc...)
5	If the content of the workshop, enablers and tools are already defined can it already be used during the required ones?	We will have a training manual and content layout for each of the sessions and workshops to share about the process - the energy aim/target will differ across regions but the content of the training will be consistent across all 4 regions - if the question was misinterpreted - please feel free to

		email directly the research lead of the Clean energy strand.
6	In the case of very big cities, is it possible to work with communities from specific parts of the city?	Yes, it is possible.
7	What proportion of Clean Energy bids are anticipated from NGOs rather than local government agencies?	We honestly have no idea - we are trying to circulate this call as far and wide as possible so we don't know who will actually complete the application.
	Efficient renovations	
	Questions	Answers
1	“a series of 3-5 ‘eco-home tours’ to frontrunners in energy efficient renovations”. Is this point referring to domestic or foreign visits? Is it up to the municipality to decide?	We expect these visits to be within the locality/region that the network is based. So, this isn't about travelling far. Ideally, actually, the hosts of these eco-home tours would actually be network members, so they are invested in the process and knowledge exchange. But, yes, it is up to you to eventually decide on where the visits/tours are. Good flexibility on the types of renovations context.
2	Can we include installment of solar PV systems on the roof of the residential buildings?	Solar PV and other building renewables can be included within a wider consideration of a whole-house approach to renovation. However, we cannot accept buildings with only renewables as being 'renovated'.
3	What is the definition of eco-tour?	An eco-tour is essentially a visit to a building that has been recently renovated. We want this to be an inspiration to participants, so ideally the renovation approach should be fairly ambitious. This will then be complemented by some pre-renovation site visits, where participants can visit a building to have a tangible discussion about what can be done and how one should approach that. This may be v attractive for someone to host because then they have many people come to those building to discuss all the possibilities and challenges.
4	Under activity 4 and 5, what do you mean by toolkit? What does it represent?	We will develop a toolkit with advice and recommendations for how to account for renovation knowhow. This will be based on the experiences of your experiments. The core partners (not you) will lead on this. Then, you will be ask at the end of your experiment to present this back to local stakeholders in your network for

		reflections.
5	Can the 10 participants of the capacity-building activities always be the same ones, in all activities?	The network as a whole (around 30 participants) must be invited to all activities, but we acknowledge that not everyone will be able to make e.g. every eco-tour, and so we have put this in as a minimum to ensure that a critical mass of the same group of participants continue engaging.
6	Do we have to focus on one context only or is it possible to combine energy poverty in urban and rural areas?	We would like you to focus on just one of those contexts. e.g. residential buildings in energy poverty in EITHER a rural or an urban area.
7	About the toolkit: will this toolkit be provided during the experiment? Or it won't, how will it work?	The core project partners (not you, as local partners) will lead on the development of this toolkit. There will be some minor input from you through your participation in the study tour, where development of this toolkit will begin in earnest.
8	Is it possible, to have financing for the conception of the events, if one is a 'lighthouse' location?	I'm not quite sure on what you mean by 'conception', but no additional funding will be provided to the lighthouse (other than study tour funds). We just expect that the lighthouse location may already have a more advanced starting point, e.g. more established local networks in this area which allow them to hit the ground running.
9	As far as I understood it, we'd need a letter of support from a certain authority or would we already have to present the stakeholders we aim to work with in the local knowledge network?	We are keen for you to demonstrate the capacity to access the relevant stakeholders. This could be done through letter of support and/or a past track record with engaging with key stakeholder groups.
10	Should the tours be free or can we ask for a small participation fee?	They will be free, as part of hosting and building the local knowledge network around renovations.
10	How do you define energy poverty and do the participants have to prove it in a way?	The definition of energy poverty is open, and no proof is required (although a brief explanation would be welcomed).
	Circular Economy	
	Questions	Answers
1	As a not-for-profit organisation interested in the circular economy call, do we need to involve entrepreneurs from a specific region/city of the country or can we connect entrepreneurs from several regions of the country?	You should build a coherent local social experiment. You can connect entrepreneurs from your region. If it is relevant, entrepreneurs from several regions of the country can be included. Be realistic, you need to ensure physical presence in the workshops.

2	Do we need LoS from businesses for our application in the circular economy call?	No, it is not necessary.
3	Do the partners for the LAH have to be established when applying?	Not necessarily.
4	When you state the word "consumer", should they be citizens or can they be other businesses?	We refer to citizens. Other businesses could be included as part of the LAH.
5	Should the ""The LAH should gather more than 10 local businesses as active participants of the platform"" requirement already been fulfilled before submission at the end of January 2023 or it can be fulfilled at the beginning of the project.	At the beginning of the project.
6	Is it correct that you'll only be funding 4 experiments - so, not necessarily in all sub-fields?	We fund 24 experiments (4 experiments under each of the 6 Streams)
7	Can some of the meetings to be organized be a distance meeting or should the 3 + prize meeting be done face to face ?	Meetings should be in-person.
	Sustainable mobility	
	Questions	Answers
1	If we pick a classroom of e.g. 5th graders for the experiment, given the timeframe of the project and that schools close in summer, how do we carry on the next "school" year (i.e. September 2023)? Do we keep the students that have moved at 6th grade or do we pick again the 5th grade (with a different group of students)?	For the process and the development of the measures and the policy recommendation, it makes sense to work with the same group of students in the next school year. However, there is no reason why new students should not be involved as well.
2	Could you please specify who is supposed to attend the training and the 12 online meetings - only the project manager or also the stakeholders and the students from the 3 schools if applying for Sustainable Mobility?	Only 1 person is funded to attend the "international" physical activities and this should be a representative of the applicant organisation. Only 1 person is required to attend the online meetings.
3	Is it possible to select three schools located in three different municipalities but	3 different cities are too complex to manage. It can be envisaged to have the 3 schools in 2 different

	belonging to the same district?	municipalities of the same metropolitan area - the main city and a smaller city.
4	How can I participate as an External Expert for Mobility in that Call? What activities of the Green Deal is an Expert eligible to participate? Is it any application I have to submit in that period?	The participation of external mobility experts is not foreseen. But you can be a subcontractor of a successful applicant to carry out some specific tasks (e.g. in the framework of a cooperation with the schools).
5	How can the rural areas be balanced in the [MOBILITY] stream with the specific location requirement of 50k+ ?	The mobility experiment is focused only on school mobility in cities or urban areas with more than 50k inhabitants.
6	We are considering applying to the sustainable mobility call, in this scope we will choose 10 students each from 3 schools which is 30 in total. The question is if we plan to make a workshop or any kind of activity in case of this call and in this project scope, should we only choose 30 students from these schools or can we invite other students other than these 30 students that we selected?	The experiment focuses on these three schools and their students. The participation of students from other schools is not foreseen.
7	Does the experiment need to cover people from 10 to 16, or is it ok if (for instance) we select 3 primary schools and the experiments are done with children aged 10 to 12?	It is okay, if you ""only"" involve young people between 10-12.
8	Perhaps we should count the FUA (functional urban area) with the core town and semi-rural or rural communities linked to its surrounding.	If this makes sense in the local context, it is possible. However, must be justified in the application form
9	Is a school eligible to apply as a non-for-profit organisation?	Yes, the school can apply as an NGO
10	Regarding shared mobility and the 50k inhabitants requirement: what if the 3 schools belong to the same metropolitan area, including several towns? How shall we count inhabitants?	Count the residents of the metropolitan area
11	There are ""comprehensive schools"" in Italy, meaning schools including several levels of education and welcoming children of different ages. Shall we consider them as single schools or as different schools?	This example is only ONE school with different levels of education. In general, with this wide age range, you could focus only for example on children between 11 and 13. But to participate in the mobility experiment you need two more schools
12	What do you exactly refer to when you ask for the city's specific modal-split in total?	The general modal split in your city (not school related): how many people in the city drive by car, take public transportation, walk & ride a bike

13	What should the letter of support signed by the local authority contain for the SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY Stream ?	It should state that the authority will support you & that the authority is interested in the results.
14	What happens if we get the letter of intent from the school now (sustainable mobility), but by the beginning of the project they change their mind? We must find alternative or e.g. we carry on with two schools?	You must find an alternative school.
15	Regarding the organization of mobility labs events for students, can we organize these sessions separately in the participating schools? The main objective of the meetings will be to develop safe routes to each school by involving the pupils of the school concerned.	In general: The social experiment forums include students from all three schools. However, during the forums you can develop specific solutions for each of the schools.
16	What if the 3 schools belong to the same metropolitan area, but are located in different towns? How shall we count inhabitants?	Count the residents of the metropolitan area
17	Can the letters of interest received from the schools adhere to the same principles as the one from the local authority (so the official letter in the local language and an English summary attached in the application)?	Sounds perfect. This will definitely enough
18	We are a ngo already working with schools and municipalities, and we already have letters of interest from 3 schools and 3 municipalities. Is it OK?	That's okay if the schools are part of ONE urban/metropolitan area.
	Sustainable Food	
	Questions	Answers
1	Who defines the questions of the 10 in depth interviews?	A set of question that are defined by the project will be supplied. We are still figuring out what it will look like in detail. It will be more like a 'semi-structured interview'. Meaning, we provide a rough structure with questions we'd like you to ask, but there is also space for

		questions you might have.
2	Is it possible to cooperate with students who conduct interviews in within their bachelor or master thesis?	As long as the interviews are in line with our requirements and of good quality, then yes it is possible.
3	We need to do 10 in-depth interviews. How long (how many pages) should one interview be?	We have not defined a particular amount of pages the interview should have. Instead we will define a set of questions that we would like you to ask, this will likely be structured as a semi-structured interview.
4	The person who is the project staff will conduct the interviews. Should it be included in the budget under point 2 ("stream specific activities") or in the costs of "human resources" (point 1 of the budget)?	It should be included in the human resources costs as one staff member of the applicant will conduct them
5	Must interviews be recorded in video?	The expectation will be that the 10 interviews you undertake will be audio recorded. We will then pay a transcription company to transcribe those recordings, before you would help us translate those transcripts. So, no to video. Yes, to audio.
6	Can you please explain a bit better who can be identified as a changemaker? Individuals, groups or both?	People/actors who are drivers to the acceleration of food transitions. This could be an individual, but this could also be an organisation, a business, etc.
7	For sustainable food I read you only have to involve 5-10 participants in your group/experiment, is that right? Before I heard around 20 participants from different organisations/stakeholder.	We aim to engage with 5-10 participants in a in-depth manner and work with them on capacities and skills needed for transitions. So we find a small(er) set of very motivated people is more important than a large set of people.
8	Should we explain in the application who each of the 5-10 changemakers will be?	No, that is not necessary yet. The recruitment will happen sometime at the start of the experiment.
9	The age group of 18-35 yo: is it for 1/3 of the target group or for all of the 5-10 key actors?	Yes, if you recruit 9 people, we want at least 3 to be between 18-34 y-old.
10	The experiment requires 4 meetings. This might be the only actions we would undertake. Where should we clarify or justify the whole process or adaption of the suggested process? (like a project plan? as an appendix?)	The 4 meetings are essential to our research process and to the transition theory we build on. You, as an applicant, can determine the content that is discussed within those meetings (to make them fit into the local context and the ideas of the participants).
11	Are the changemakers to be identified locally or should they be selected from a broader area? (say, national level)	We can discuss how to define local in this case. This could be national - if this is the most relevant scale for your country. Or .. let's say, 'hyper-local', from your

		municipality or city, if that fits the food system challenge you would like to work on.
12	Is it OK if the changemaker is president of the applying NGO ?	Yes, that is fine. The president of the NGO could then leverage their network (and through this process also expand their network) to make these sustainable food experiments successful.
13	Is the only target of the food stream young participants?	
14	In the case of sustainable food the call mentions the involment of 15-20 local food system change makers, but in the presentation it was mentioned 5-10. Which number should we consider?	Correct, this was a typo we only spotted yesterday (and have corrected). We are aiming to convene 5-10 very motivated change makers. But obviously we hope that you are able to recruit 10 highly motivated change makers!
15	Could you please give more detailed information about the action agenda in this stream?	The action agenda is essentially a list of concrete points/actions that will support the acceleration of a local food transition. The local change makers will co-create/define over the course of a year.
16	Can we pay the change makers to participate in the workshops or is it expected that they participate for free?	This depends on how you plan to manage your budget.. In general, we do not pay people, but provide an expense-paid process that will help participants build a network and the capacities to accelerate a food transition. This is why we ask you to recruit 5-10 highly motivated change makers.
17	Related to the 10 in-depth interviews with the local target stakeholders and citizens of the local experiments, I understand we need to develop 10 interviews with the local target only, or we should develop additional interviews with other citizens?	Stream dependant, for the food-stream, we want you to interview the change-makers that you will recruit. Yes, you need to commit to undertake 10 in-depth interviews with the local target stakeholders and citizens of the social experiment INCLUDING translating the questions from English into your local language and the answers into English. Interview resources and transcripts will be provided by the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.
18	What is funded with the grant within this stream?	The 4 preparation, organisation of meetings, but also the other requirements we have outlined. So the undertaking the interviews, attending progress meetings with us, and more general administrative tasks for the project and data collection for the project. Please feel free to include other relevant activities if needed to build a coherent local social experiment that answers your local needs and challenges (within the 22 000 EUR budget limit).
19	We'd like to outsource a partner organisation to support with the recruitment of changemakers (sustainable food call). Is that allowed?	If that fits within your budget, it is fine to have a partner organisation support with particular portions of the experiments.
20	Since you are providing the guidelines for the	We expect the interviews to

	interviews, how long will they be/Is there a minimum time they have to be in order to be ""useable""? (I'm thinking of academic requirements where interviews have to be X Minutes long in order for the answers to be useable later on).	take around 45 minutes and we have budgetted roughly 60 minutes for transcription of the interviews.
21	In the framework of the planned activity on sustainable food topic, there will be 4 meetings. These meetings can be attended only by the group of the local food system changers (transition committee, 15-20 people) or it can be a larger event where several stakeholders (farmers, producers) can participate?	The requirement is to recruit at least 5-10 highly motivated change makers - that is the 'base' requirement. And the meetings focus on capacity building for transition management for these change makers. If you see a way to include more actors in a way that is feasible and still makes sure this core group is engaged in an in-depth way, then it is possible to make it a larger event.
22	About the 5 - 10 local changemakers, should it always be on an individual person basis? Or could it also be for example a department of an university?	These changemakers can be individuals, but they could also be organisations or initiatives. It is important that you recruit a diverse set of people though. So 1 from a university is fine.. but not all.
23	Will these 5-10 highly motivated change makers on sustainable food attend all of the 4 meetings?	Yes, the idea is that they become a small network. So it is vital they are engaged throughout the 4 meetings.
24	Do we as a non-for-profit organisation in the food stream not have to attach a letter of support to our application?	Everyone needs to submit a letter of support from their local authority, that is a general requirement.
25	Do we already need to know who we will recruit for the sustainable food stream?	No. There is a specific time reserved for the recruitment of people in the beginning of the experiment. all that is required is that you recruit a diverse group of change makers. so e.g. a farmer, a business owner, a researcher, etc...
26	What do you mean by "local food system": growing food or storage?	The idea is to focus is on the local food system - what this means, depends on what is relevant for your location. So this could be the national food system and change makers that work in that context.. or a the city- context, along with change makers that are relevant to that context.
27	Who is paying for which translation (of the interviews)? (in order to make a correct budget)	The (time needed for) transcription of the interviews needs to be included in the experiment budget, under staff costs or subcontracting (depending on how you get organised). the translation should be included in the 22 000 EUR budget you have available.
28	Is their a specific time when the meetings should take place (such as in Month	

	X, Y,,Z)? or does it really depend on local context?	
	Biodiversity	
	Questions	Answers
1	What is the expected format of field studies and what is the content of their reports?	Format of field studies are open for co-design with participants and they can change. Reporting should encompass the topics of the discussions held, interesting points raised, etc...
2	How will the duration of study group lessons be determined?	Around 2 hours, depending on how the process goes.
3	What should the group meeting look like in the first month of project implementation? Can it be transferred to the second month of the project? (The first month can be spent on group formation).	Study Circle participant recruitment is done in April 2023, the SC starts in May 2023.
4	What is the structure of an in-depth panel interview? When should it be carried out within the framework of the project?	We will prepare the questions of the interview, you will only have to translate these questions to local language and interview the participants (recording) of the SC. The interviews are planned to take place before the last public event, i.e. appr. April 2024.
5	Are there any restrictions on the persons who are planned to be involved in the study? Is it necessary to involve NGOs if they do not exist within the community? Is it possible to involve young people who are state authorities (deputies)?	No restrictions. Though the Key citizens group are adults in different age groups involving women and those who suffered isolation during the COVID-19 pandemic.
6	What is the meaning of adults who may have experienced isolation?	Ideally we would like a representation of people who have suffered from isolation due to the Covid-19 pandemic or the pandemic has influenced their life in a significant manner. However, it is enough to involve 1-5 such people per SC.
7	As far as I understand this call, we will get an education material (Study Circles) to use and we have to use this for the stakeholders and involved 15 people?	In the training you will be trained on how to implement SC, but you will not get material on biodiversity. You will have to craft this together with participants during 10 meetings.
8	A series of meetings is mentioned. Are there any requirements as to the number of meetings?	There need to be at least 10 Study Circles conducted within 1 year.

9	Is the co-design of an adult education programme a non-formal education programme?	Yes, it is an informal education programme.
10	Would a specific case study around a biodiversity problem, like nature restoration, for example be adequate?	It can be one of the themes of the Study Circles indeed, but there is an adequate level of freedom to co-design the focus of your Study Circle.
11	How do you define regions? In our context (danish) regions mainly administer transport and health care, so municipalities would seem like more obvious partners.	Municipalities are eligible entities indeed.
12	What exactly does the co-design entail? Does it mean that you design it with the study circle participants, with other stakeholders or all or none of the above?	It refers to co-design with the participants. The topic and focus of the discussions, format of field visits, etc. are open to co-design with them.
13	What do you have in mind when you talk about counteracting biodiversity loss? How direct do you expect it to be?	There is no expectation, but investigate how by shifting the values we place upon biodiversity can we actually act against biodiversity loss (shifts in personal life, change of behaviour regarding the matter, etc.).
14	One of the overall commitments needed to comply with concerning this call, is to undertake 10 in-depth interviews with the local target stakeholders and citizens of the social experiment. Will these interviews made collective or individual?	Individual.
15	It is allowed to pay participants of the workshops through the grant. Should this expense inserted on point 2 of the budget has "others" for the study circle adult learning meetings?	Yes, these are eligible costs, so you can include them in the budget expenses. However, as the study circles approach is based on voluntary basis, we expect participants join the group because they wish to learn more about biodiversity.
16	Do the 10-15 adults have to always be the same? or can they be different during the 12 month periode?	The group should be the same from the first to the last meeting. The idea is that we can measure if the study circle approach is useful to induce changes in values upon biodiversity. Though it can happen that someone drops out during the process, so a sub-contractor should motivate people to come.
17	Do we have to designate an already existing area (e.g. a park in the city, or trail in the forest, etc) we want to preserve in the proposal or could it be decided later?	The area must be already designated in the proposal.

18	Do all participants have to be from the same region and do all activities have to take place in the same region?	The participants remain the same for the duration of all the experiment (i.e. all 10 Study Circles). The field visits or Study Circles can take place in various locations within the country if participants are willing to co-design such an activity.
19	We will get an education material (Study Circles) to use and we have to use this for the stakeholders and involved 15 people? Can you summarize it briefly?	The study circle is an approach of informal adult education, i.e. adults who want to learn more about biodiversity will come to the 1 year experiment. This group stays the same since the beginning. The sub-contractor will act as civil society mentor which has to engage 10 to 15 people interested to learn. We will not prepare material related to biodiversity, the participants will tell what they want to learn related to biodiversity. There will be opportunity to invite experts on biodiversity to give specificity information regarding biodiversity.
20	We were thinking to involve in our project as a target group the representatives of the different neighbourhoods in Lisbon. This could ensure a positive spread of the social experiment results within the different parts of the city. Because we are addressing the decision-making level, we cannot control the inclusiveness. Should we change target group?	If they are all adults and willing to participate in a 1 year experiment yes you could use them. Though bear in mind you should also involve a small number of vulnerable people (suffered from isolation during covid pandemic).
21	Can the participants be based in all regions of the country as well?	The participants need to meet physically every month, this is one Study Circle. If it is possible to implement such an activity with participants from all regions of the country then you are welcome to.
22	Part B - Where will your local social experiment take place? Define the geographical characteristics of the area - Question: Is there any preferences for the selected area, eg. rural, urban or for example area with ongoing restructuring process?	At the end we should take care to involve urban and rural areas, so at the time of selection this will be taken into consideration. Though you should justify the selection of your location.
23	About the biodiversity stream, are just 10 interviews with target group required? or do we have to carry out additional interviews with other interested people?	10 interviews with the participants of the Study Circles are required.
24	What would happen if some of the adults engaged in the study circles leave the process midway, e.g. due to other commitments? Is there any problem if the participants numbers falls at	This is the work of the applicant: assemble a group of participants who are willing to meet monthly for a year. A number of drop-outs is foreseen, but the success of the Study Circles relies on the continuous engagement

	some point below the required minimum due to this? I understand that it might be not feasible to add new members half-way through the process since they would be missing all the previous work.	of the participants.
25	How often do participants have to get involved in the experiment throughout the year? Is twice per week enough for instance?	During social experiments 10 meetings, 1 per month are foreseen.
26	To be sure how you define a "study circle". For the project we envision there would be many meetings out in the nature, visiting and exploring different sites, and trying different types of activities. I.e. sometimes very practical, sometimes more discussions-oriented and presentations-oriented etc... Would these all count as "study circle meetings"?	Yes! Participants need to show a strong engagement during the discussions, space needs to be given to them to co-design their final event, areas of focus of discussions, etc... However, a loose program of social experiment activities given in the Implementation plan should be followed.
27	Can my social experiment (study circles) be located in all locations (protected landscape, urban land, rural cultural landscape)?	That is possible.
28	How can we justify that the 5 adults have experienced isolation?	During their testimonies during interviews, discussions held during the study circles, etc...
29	Can we have 2 groups of study circles?	We need 1 study circle, 10-15 participants.
30	Why are the COVID-isolated people important for the study circle ?	One of the main messages of the EU Green Deal is that the transition needs to be just, fair and inclusive, therefore we would like to explore how such individuals have experienced isolation and if their connection with nature has changed because of that. Have their values linked to biodiversity changed because of the pandemic?

This document will be updated as additional FAQs are submitted and answered - see section 9.